

QUIZ**LAST NAME: MAWIRE****FIRST NAME: SIMBARASHE****PROGRAM CODE: ACA-401****COURSE CODE : MDIA****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What are the five components of an essay paragraph as identified in ACA-401 course-pack?**
 - Correct US or UK spelling, introduction, body, in-text citation and conclusion
 - Topic sentence, supporting sentence, evidence, analysis and critical conclusion.¹**
 - Subheading, topic sentence, evidence, in-text citation and conclusion.
 - All the above.

1. EUCLID. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period One*. (Euclid University, 2019),4. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1> (accessed January 04, 2020).

2. **What is the EUCLID University recommended referencing style guide for major papers?**

- Turabian' Manual for writers of research papers, theses, and dissertations (Turabian & Chicago Rule of Style).²**
- American Psychological Associations (APA).
- Harvard Rule of Style.
- Oxford Rule of Style.

3. **What is the main difference between primary and secondary source?**

- Primary source has more information than secondary source.
- Secondary source is more reliable than primary source.
- Secondary source of information can be traced no more than its author, whereas, primary source can be traced beyond its author.
- Primary source of information can be traced to no more than its author, whereas secondary source can be traced beyond its author.³**

4. **At what point of your paper should you write the title of your paper.**

- Title is the last thing I write as it is built around the content of my entire paper.⁴**
- Title is the first thing I must write.
- After researching the topic, I want to write about.

2. Ibid., 24.

3. Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Writing Source 2000: A Guide to Writing Thinking and Learning* (Massachusetts: Greta Source Education, 1999), 263.

4 . Turabian, Kate L., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations* (Chicago: University of Chicago, 2013), 73.

- There is no formal requirement, as such I can right it at any given point.

5. **When writing a sentence, I should focus on what?**

- The strong use of vocabulary.
- My research results and evidence.
- The first seven to eight words of a sentence.⁵**
- The first seven sentences.

6. **What are the four reasons for citing your sources?**

- To give credit to the authors, to assure readers about the accuracy of your facts, to show readers the research traditions that informs your work, to help readers follow or extend your research.⁶**
- To give credit to the author, to assure readers about the accuracy of your facts, so that readers do not question my opinion, to demonstrate my analytical skills.
- To convince readers and gain their buy-in, to extend the famousness of the authors, to assure readers about the accuracy of your acts, to show readers the research traditions that informs your work.
- To extend the famousness of the authors, to assure readers about the accuracy of your facts, to show readers the research traditions that informs your work, to avoid negative criticism from readers.

7. **In the United States, before 1874, laws were published in the what?**

5. Ibid., 74.

6. Ibid., 86.

- Annual Bound Volumes of the United States at Large.
- Seventeenth-volume Statute at Large of the United States of America.**⁷
- United States Code.
- Annals of the Congress of the United States.

8. **Where can ellipsis be used during writing your research report?**

- When I have run out of words to say.
- When there is missing or omitted text from a quotation or to indicate a pause for effect.**⁸
- When you use a direct quotation.
- When you have paraphrased an idea.

9. **What Treaty was signed on 13 December 2007?**

- Treaty of Lisbon.**⁹
- Treaty of Nice.
- Treaty of Amsterdam.
- Treaty of European Union.

7. Ibid., 124.

8. University of Oxford. *University of Oxford Style Guide*. (University of Oxford, 2014), 15. <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/YIJXVLgPv0/> (accessed February 24, 2020).

9. European Commission. 2011. *English Style Guide*. <https://euclid.egnyte.com/dl/xitMjHAGfJ/> (accessed March 10, 2020), 54.

10. As specified in Article 288 of the Treaty on the Function of the European Union's secondary legislations, which legislations are directly binding in all EU Member States?

Regulations and Decisions.¹⁰

Treaty of European Union.

Regulations and Directives.

Decisions and Directives.

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10. Ibid., 56.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.